

SURKHAN OASIS IN THE WORKS OF LOCAL ARTISTS ANALYSIS OF ECONOMIC LIFE

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the works created by local historians of the end of the XIX century and the beginning of the XX century, and with the help of these works, the history of the socio-political, economic, military and cultural life of the Bukhara Emirate was analyzed on the basis of comparison and historical consistency.*

Key words: *Emirate of Bukhara, historians, Muhammad Vafoyi Karminaghi, Ahmad Donish, Mirza Salimbek, Sayyid Olimkhan.*

АНАЛИЗ ХОЗЯЙСТВЕННОЙ ЖИЗНИ СУРХАНСКОГО ОАЗИСА В ТРУДАХ КРАЕВЕДОВ

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Аннотация: *В данной статье анализируются труды, созданные краеведами конца XIX века и начала XX века, и с помощью этих трудов исследуется история общественно-политической, экономической, военной и культурной жизни Бухарский эмират анализировался на основе сравнения и исторической непротиворечивости.*

Ключевые слова: *Бухарский эмират, историки, Мухаммад Вафойи Карминаги, Ахмад Дониш, Мирзо Салимбек, Сайид Олимхан.*

The works of local historians are important in studying the history of the Bukhara Emirate and the colonial era of the Russian Empire [1. 56,151]. The authors of these works directly saw that period with their own eyes and are a collection of works and information created by the participants of the events.

Today, in terms of their value and importance, these works are at the level of rare manuscript sources and researches. Among the local written sources are “Khan`s Gift” or “Tarihi Rahimkhani” (History of Muhammad Rahim Khan) [2] by Muhammad Vafoyi Karminaghi, “Tarihi Amir Haidar” (History of Amir Haidar) by Mulla Ibodullah and Mulla Muhammad Sharif [3], Mir “Fathnomai sultani” (Fathnoma of the Sultan) by scholar Bukhari [4. 239], Ahmad Mahdumi Donish`s “Brief treatise on the history of the dynasty of the Mangit kingdom” [5. 92], “Biographical situation of the emir of Bukhara” (written after 1885), “History of the Mangit dynasty”) [6. 274]. Mirza Abdulazim Sami Bostaniy (1838 /39-after 1914) “History of Mangit Sultanate” [7. 109], Mirza Salimbek (full name: Mirza Salimbek ibn Muhammad Rahim) “History of Salimi” [8], “Useful history” of Muhammad Ali Baljuvani [9. 2] was also used as a historical source.

Necessary information about the political, economic, social and cultural life of the oasis, as well as the geography, topography and ethnic names of the territories dominated by the Mangits are given in Mirzo Abdulazim Sami`s “History of the Mangit Empire”. Mirzo Abdulazim Sami Bostaniy (1839 – Bukhara, Boston village (now Kyziltepa district) – b1908) historian, scientist, calligrapher. He studied in Bukhara madrasas. With the advice of his teacher Qazi Sa`diddin Mahir [10], he received the nickname Sami - “noble, high” [11]. At first, he worked in the palace of Bukhara emirs, especially during the reign of Emir Muzaffar (1860 – 1885) and Emir Abdulahad (1885 – 1910) as a palace munshi.

According to Mirza Abdulazim Sami, Amir Muzaffar established a friendly relationship with the Russian governor in Eastern Bukhara and started his military campaigns to replace the lost Zarafshan oasis, secondly because he supported Abdulmalik's network, and thirdly, taking into account the strategic location of the area. In order to take revenge on the bells and court tribes of the Sherabad principality, he first appointed Karshi Beg Abdumomintora and Yaqub Koshbegi as the governor of Guzor and sent them to Sherabad with an armed army.

In many places of this work, Mirza Abdulazim Sami also provides information about local rulers, beks and landowners. We can see positive opinions about historical figures in the works of local historians. It aims to illuminate the history of socio-political, economic, military and cultural life in the center of Bukhara Emirate. This situation requires a critical evaluation and analysis of most of the data and conclusions in the literature belonging to the third group. In these studies, the role of the Bekliks of the Surkhan oasis in the political, socio-economic life of the Bukhara Emirate in the late 19th - early 20th centuries (based on the materials of the Bukhara “Qoshbegi” archive) is poorly covered, and some of them are important in illuminating some aspects of the studied topic. The main part of the scientific researches related to the

Soviet era is the research conducted on the eastern regions of the Bukhara Emirate, that is, eastern Bukhara [12].

One of the greatest representatives of the historiographical school of this period is the enlightener Ahmad ibn Nasir ibn Yusuf al-Hanafi al-Siddiq, known as Ahmad Donish. Ahmad Donish Makhdum ibn Nasir (1827 – Bukhara – 1897) writer, artist, calligrapher, scientist, enlightener. Born in a Mudarris family. In the 19th century, Bukhara played an important role in the emergence of a progressive environment. He thoroughly mastered the religious and secular sciences of his time. In the 1850 s, he worked as a calligrapher and architect in the palace of Amir Nasrullah (1826 – 1860), and later rose to the rank of chief architect. Ahmed Donish, who has visited the Russian Empire three times, compares the society of Bukhara, which has entered a new stage of development, with Russia, which is a relatively advanced country, which is going through depression, and decides that reforms should be carried out in the emirate. He wrote a work entitled “Risola dar nazmi tamaddun va taovun” (A treatise on culture and mutual assistance) and presented it to the emir.

Researchers named this work “Political treatise”. In his pamphlet, the idea of reforming the state and society of Bukhara on the basis of legality and humanity was boldly put forward. Naturally, the emir did not like these progressive ideas of Ahmad Donish and accused him of “indoctrination” and appointed him as a judge in Guzor in 1882. With this, Ahmad Donish will be removed from the capital. Ahmad Donish, who returned to Bukhara after the death of Amir Muzaffar, devoted the rest of his life only to creativity. Ahmadi Makhdum Donish`s work on the history of the Bukhara Emirate “Treatise or summary of the history of the Mangit dynasty” is also known as “Historical treatise”, and the thinker`s political, social and educational views are expressed in great detail. This treatise is the first part of the work that the scientist could not finish. Due to the incompleteness of the work, according to its content, the researchers left the names “History” and “Biography of Mangit Amirs”.

In the manuscript treasure of the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Republic of Uzbekistan, about twenty works of the scientist on history, astronomy, geography and other sciences are stored. Donish`s works “Navodir al-waqae” (Rare events) and “Tarjimai ahvoli amironi Bukharai sharif az Amir Daniyal to asri Amir Abdulahad” (Biographies of the emirs of Bukhara from Amir Daniyal to Amir Abdulahad) occupy the main place in his scientific and literary heritage. Philosophical, political and historical views of the author are reflected in these works. He finished writing his next work, also known as “Risola yo mukhtasare az tarikhi sultanati khanadoni mangitiya”, at the end of his life, that is, in the 90 s of the XIX century. “Historical Treatise” is full of interesting and important information. For example, the proposed project for the economic development of the country, thoughts about water supply to Bukhara and its

surroundings, memories of his trip to Russia are among these. This work presents the rulers of the Mangit dynasty in the Emirate of Bukhara, their policies in managing the state, the lifestyle of the population in the territory of the Emirate, and other interesting information.

The last Bukhara emir Sayyid Olimkhan (1910 – 1920) wrote “The History of the Tragedy of the Bukhara People” from the days when the emir was a student of science, the time of the Emirate, the violent occupation of Bukhara by the Bolsheviks, and his life away from the homeland, until the years of emigration. clearly manifested [13.1,2].

Based on the information presented in the work, at that time, the state of Bukhara was divided into twenty-eight provinces. For example, today's places like Nurota, Karakol, Chorjoi, Shahrisabz, Kitab, Guzor, Denov, Yakkabog, each consisted of a beklík. Beklik corresponds to rayon (district) in our current usage.

According to Amir Olimkhan, at that time, the land belonging to the Bukhara state was 225,000 square kilometers. The population consisted mainly of Uzbeks, Turkmens, Kyrgyz, Kazakhs, Tajiks, Jews and Arabs. According to the author, “The khans of Bukhara were completely from the Uzbek category of Mangits. The kings of Bukhara were seated on a bed (made of white felt) according to the Mongol customs, and the Sayyids, Khojas and Mullahs lifted them from the ground”. Carrying Turkish kings in white felt was a long-standing tradition.

Muhammad Ali Baljuvani`s “History of Nafei” provides important information about the Bukhara Emirate at the beginning of the 20th century. The state system of the emirate, the method of administration, the political events that took place during 1918-1922 were described by the witness. The work contains important information about the political situation in the cities of Denov, Boysun, Sarijoi, Sariosia, and Sherabad.

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